

LINGUISTICS - IN A LINGUISTOCULTURAL ASPECT

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Abstract. *This article discusses the current state of linguistic and cultural studies, one of the most developed areas in the world, in particular in Russian linguistics, and significant research has been done in this area. In the works of this area, it can be observed that researchers pay great attention to such issues as the linguistic landscape of the world, linguistic and cultural concepts, linguistic and cultural codes, precedent units, intertextuality, linguistic consciousness, and the linguistic and cultural characteristics of stable units.*

Keywords: *linguistics, world, linguistics, field, research, universe, linguistic, landscape, concept, code, precedent, unity, intertextuality, linguistic consciousness, stable unity, feature.*

ЛИНГВИСТИКА - В ЛИНГВОКУЛЬТУРНОМ АСПЕКТЕ

Аннотация. *В статье рассматривается современное состояние лингвистики и культурологии, одного из самых развитых направлений в мире, в частности в русистике, и в этой области проведены значительные исследования. В работах этого направления можно заметить, что исследователи уделяют большое внимание таким вопросам, как языковой ландшафт мира, лингвокультурные концепты, лингвокультурные коды, прецедентные единицы, интертекстуальность, языковое сознание, лингвокультурные характеристики устойчивых единиц.*

Ключевые слова: *лингвистика, мир, лингвистика, поле, исследование, вселенная, лингвистический, ландшафт, концепт, код, прецедент, единство, интертекстуальность, языковое сознание, устойчивое единство, признак.*

The main goal of linguocultural studies is to study the reflection in language of culture, national thought, and the specific aspects of its perception of the world. The object of this field is language and culture, and the subject matter is linguistic units that reflect cultural semantics. Therefore, linguistic and cultural studies study language units that carry cultural information. Such language units are grouped under the term linguocultural units. Symbol, mythologema, etalon, metaphor, paremiological units, lacunae, stereotypes, precedent units, speech labels, and

linguocultural codes are considered basic linguocultural units. The main task of linguistic and cultural research is to describe and identify linguistic units that reflect the national-cultural mentality of language speakers, cultural archetypes that correspond to the ancient ideas of humanity, national sociocultural stereotypes characteristic of speech communication, the linguistic landscape of the world, the conceptsphere, which is a set of basic concepts of culture, and linguistic consciousness. [1;8-9]

Today, linguistic and cultural studies is one of the most developed areas in the world, in particular in Russian linguistics, and significant research has been created in this area. In the works of this field, it can be observed that researchers pay great attention to such issues as the linguistic landscape of the world, linguistic and cultural concepts, linguistic and cultural codes, precedent units, intertextuality, linguistic consciousness, and linguocultural properties of stable units. In such studies, a completely new interpretation and analysis of all levels of language, in particular words and texts, is a priority. The study of linguistic units not only from the perspective of linguistic laws, but also from the perspective of factors such as society, man, culture, spirituality, and national mentality has led to the emergence of new ideas, new scientific views, and principles in linguistics. The ideas about the unity of language and culture have been mentioned in one way or another in the works of scholars who laid the foundation stone of Uzbek linguistics and made a significant contribution to its development. However, it is worth noting that the serious and systematic implementation of linguistic and cultural analysis of language in our linguistics began in the second decade of the 21st century.

The first articles on linguistic and cultural studies were published in the journal "Uzbek Language and Literature" by N. Mahmudov, E. Begmatov, and A. Nurmonov. [2; 35-39;]. Professor N. Mahmudov's article "In Search of Ways to Perfectly Study Language..." provides a thorough and well-founded explanation of the essence of the field of linguistic and cultural studies and the problems in this regard. [3; 3-16]. The article presents well-founded considerations about the factors that served to form the linguocultural theory, its main concepts, and the differences in their interpretation. The scientist's article "Similarities - a product of figurative thinking" is of great importance in that it determines the relationship of stable similes in the Uzbek language to language and speech, and also defines them as "units that reflect the national figurative way of thinking" [4; 19-24], and poses the problem of studying the linguistic and cultural characteristics of such figurative units.

N. Mahmudov further elaborated on this point in his preface to the "Explanatory Dictionary of Uzbek Language Analogies." [5; 10-19]. In 2015, a doctoral dissertation was defended on the topic "Anthropocentric interpretation of literary texts in the Uzbek language." Chapter 3 of this study, which presents ideas about the theoretical foundations of the anthropocentric paradigm, is devoted to the analysis of texts in the Uzbek language from a linguocultural aspect, in which a linguocultural analysis of text-metaphors and text-analyses is carried out. The study proposes to classify metaphors into 4 types (word metaphors, compound metaphors, sentence metaphors, and textual metaphors), and to recognize the stable patterns of texts as the 5th type of precedent units. [6;44].

In Uzbek linguistics, the principles of anthropocentric research have also begun to find their reflection in dictionaries. In the "Explanatory Dictionary of Uzbek Language Analogies" [7;3-10], compiled under the leadership of Nizomiddin Mahmudov, the linguocultural characteristics of more than 500 stable analogies in our language were first highlighted. This dictionary demonstrates the national figurative thinking of the Uzbek people, their way of perceiving the world, and their axiological attitude to reality through the use of stable analogies in the Uzbek language. In 2015, the dictionary on linguistic and cultural studies [8;240] explained the meaning of more than 200 key terms in this field.

At the beginning of our century, several dissertation studies on linguoculturology were also carried out. [9;147, 10;129, 11;151]. The main attention in these dissertations was paid to the study of linguocultural units. For example, in the dissertation work on the topic "Linguo-cultural study of similes in the Uzbek language" conducted by Usmanov Farhod, the role of national-cultural connotation in the semantics of stable similes in the Uzbek language was clarified, the images that serve as the standard of similes were grouped in a linguo-cultural approach and illuminated from the point of view of linguo-cultural codes, and based on the analysis of stable similes in the Uzbek language, aspects specific to the cultural norms and axiological attitude of the Uzbek nation were identified. [12;161]. In general, it is worth saying that in our linguistics, serious research has emerged in the field of linguocultural studies, the terminology of the field has been consolidated, and its theoretical foundations have been improved. At the same time, it is appropriate to recognize that there are a number of problems in this area, and certain tasks need to be implemented in this regard.

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